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The Relationship Between Microbiota and Metabolic Diseases in the Elderly People

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ABSTRACT

The gut microbiota plays a crucial role in the development and management of metabolic syndrome in the elderly. Aging is associated with changes in the gut microbiota composition, which can lead to metabolic disorders like obesity and related conditions. These alterations in the microbiome can trigger low-grade inflammation and innate immunity activation, contributing to metabolic diseases commonly seen in the elderly population. Studies have shown that alterations in the gut microbiota composition are associated with metabolic syndrome components such as obesity, insulin resistance, and inflammation. Probiotics have been investigated for their potential to improve metabolic health in the elderly, showing promising results in reducing waist circumference, insulin levels, cholesterol, and inflammatory markers. Furthermore, illnesses such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's have been linked to changes in the gut microbiome, with microbiota-derived metabolites playing a role in influencing cognitive defects and age-associated pathologies. Therefore, understanding and modulating the gut microbiota through interventions like probiotics and dietary adjustments can be crucial in managing metabolic diseases and promoting healthy aging in the elderly. Specific bacterial genera like *Prevotella*, *Bacteroides*, and *Lachnospiraceae* have been linked to weight loss and metabolic health improvements in older adults. Understanding the relationship between gut microbiota and metabolic syndrome in the elderly is crucial for developing targeted interventions to improve their metabolic health and overall well-being. The interaction between gut microbiota and metabolic diseases has gained significant attention in recent research. Herbal medicines have been shown to influence gut microbial composition, intestinal barrier function, inflammation, and microbial metabolites, thereby impacting metabolic disorders positively. Additionally, studies have highlighted the therapeutic potential of modulating the gut microbiome through approaches like probiotics, prebiotics, synbiotics, and fecal microbiota transplantation in managing metabolic disorders such as diabetes and obesity. Furthermore, the modulation of gut microbiota through fecal microbiota transplantation has shown promise in treating endocrine and intestinal inflammatory diseases, emphasizing the importance of regulating the microbiome for improved health outcomes. All of these results highlight how important the microbiome is as a possible target for metabolic illness treatment. In the treatment of metabolic diseases; while treating insulin resistance, atherosclerosis, and lipid metabolism disorders, treatments targeting the gut microbiota, our largest endocrine organ, should also be planned. Especially in diseases such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, dyslipidemia, and obesity, probiotic and prebiotic-based nutrition should be emphasized. Large-scale multicenter studies on humans, especially probiotics, are inadequate, and the studies have different results because the microbiota varies according to the individual, lifestyle, and geographical conditions. In the years to come, within the framework of technological developments and global research, the effectiveness of microbiota in treatment will be better understood and new horizons in treatment will be opened.

Keywords: Elderly people, gut microbiota, metabolic syndrome, probiotics